

Local Government in Ethiopia

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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1. The System of Local Government in Ethiopia

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Types of Local Governments

The Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia (FDRE) Constitution has established a federal state structure composed of nine ethnic based constituent units namely: Tigray, Afar, Amhara, Oromia, Somali, Benishangul/Gumuz, Gmbella, Southern Nations, Nationalities and Peoples (SNNP) and Harari. Ethiopia is a dual federal state since Article 50(1) of the Constitution stipulates as The Federal democratic Republic of Ethiopia comprises the federal government and the state members. Local government is not explicitly stipulated by the Federal Constitution which remains almost silent. This paves the way to the constituent units to enjoy unlimited constitutional space in the area. Article 50(4) of the federal Constitution merely states that ‘State government shall be established at the state and other administrative levels that they (i.e. the regional states) find necessary’. In fact, the second sentence of the article gives a specific federal mandate to the region and reads ‘Adequate power shall be granted to the lowest units of government to enable the people to participate directly in the administration of such units’. This implies the Constitution has implicitly provided for the establishment of non-ethnic local governments.

In addition, Article 39(3) states that Every Nation, Nationality and People in Ethiopia has the right to a full measure of self-government which includes the right to establish institutions of government in the territory that it inhabits’. According to this article, local governments are established along ethnic lines for ethnic groups which are basically ‘ethnic local government’.¹ Here, the Federal Constitution poses a duty on the regional states to realize genuine self-government and ample amount of decentralization of power to the local levels. Accordingly, all regional state constitutions have provisions related to local government with a relative uniformity.

As mentioned above, the constitutional recognition of local government in Ethiopia has remained debatable. Despite this debate, local governments are constitutionally recognized at least implicitly. If one gets a closer look to the provisions of the Federal Constitution, it

¹ Zemelak A Ayele and Yonatan T Fessha, ‘The Constitutional Status of Local Government in Federal Systems: The Case of Ethiopia’ (2012) 58 Africa Today 89, 93.

envisaged the establishment of two kinds of local governments: ethnic and regular.² These two categories of local governments have two distinct objectives.³ Ethnic local governments aim at realizing the self-determination rights stipulated under Article 39(3) of the Federal Constitution. Practically these local governments are established in the name of ‘nationality zones’ or ‘special *woreda*’ in all regional states except Oromia, Harari and Somali. On the other hand, the regular local governments are established by the regional states as per the Federal Constitution’s provision of Article 50(4) in the name of *zone*, *woreda* (city/town administration) and *kebele*.

Regarding administrative structure, all regional states, except Harari⁴, are composed of three levels of local governments: nationality (*zone*), special (*woreda*) and *kebele*. Nationality *zones*, *woredas*, special *woredas* and *kebeles* have three tiers of institutional structure composed of a council; administrative council and judicial body.⁵ Zones are administrative levels just below the regional state comprising a number of districts (*woredas*) or urban centers. Unlike nationality *zones*, regular *zones* are founded by ordinary legislation with no council in Amhara, Oromia, Somali, Afar and Tigray regional states. It is a deconcentrated administrative body of the regional state. The *woreda* is the local government level standing next to the zone, encompassing *kebeles* and administratively subordinate and accountable to both the zone and regional state. *Kebele* is the lowest local government level included in all regional state constitutions. There are two categories of urban local governments: cities and towns. ‘Cities’ signifies the two cities under the federal jurisdiction (Addis Ababa and Dire Dawa). There are urban centers named by the legislations of their respective regional state councils. Towns are urban centers located beneath the zonal administrative structure and ranges from small to large based on their population size. Unlike others, small and medium towns may have a *woreda* status and in each *woreda*, there is a town from which the *woreda* is administered.⁶

Legal Status of Local Governments

Institutional security of local government is a crucial element of political autonomy of local government.⁷ In order to protect the existence of local government as a sphere or level of government from the encroachment of the central government, constitutional recognition is

² Zemelak A Ayele, ‘The Existence of Local Government and its Institutional Security within Ethiopia’s Federal System’ in Asnake Kefale and Assefa Fiseha (eds), *Federalism and Local Government in Ethiopia* (UNDP and Center for Federal Studies 2015) 203.

³ *ibid.*

⁴ Harary regional state is composed of only two levels of governments: regional state and *kebele*.

⁵ Christophe Van der Beken, *Completing the Constitutional Architecture: A Comparative Analysis of Subnational Constitutions in Ethiopia* (Addis Ababa University Press 2017) 141.

⁶ WSUP Advisory, ‘Developing an Integrated Urban Sanitation and Hygiene Strategy and Strategic Action Plan for Ethiopia’ (Draft Situational Analysis for Ethiopia’s IUSHS) 20.

⁷ Ayele, ‘The Existence of Local Government and its Institutional Security within Ethiopia’s Federal System’, above, 202.

recommended as an effective formal mechanism.⁸ Political autonomy also entails uninterrupted existence of local government. The constitutional recognition of local government as an autonomous level of government does not only resist the intrusions from other levels but it also enhances the political and economic role that local government ought to play. Accordingly, local government administrations are supposed to be autonomous units. However, no constitutionally entrenched functions meet the above standards in the Ethiopian federal tradition. The Federal Constitution leaves this to the regional states to determine tiers, powers and functions.

As an element of political autonomy, local government functional competencies should be original, clearly defined, and development-related.⁹ This is usually achieved through providing constitutional guarantees and full power to local governments on those functions. Considering the dual nature of the Ethiopian Constitution, local government units do not have original functions.¹⁰ Rather their functions are determined by regional states.

(A) Symmetry of the Local Government System

Despite the fact that both typologies of local governments lack original autonomy, there is some kind of asymmetry between urban local governments and other regular (*woreda*) and ethnic (nationality zone and special *woreda*) local governments. The state constitutions constrained the councils of the latter in law-making powers. On the other hand, urban councils are empowered to issue policy and regulations of their own.¹¹ Accordingly, medium and large towns have enjoyed special status as compared to *woreda* governments having larger population. Moreover, a kind of paradox has arisen as the city councils which are under the supervision of the nationality *zone* council have a law-making power while the latter is restricted to its specific implementation guidelines.

Political and Social Context in Ethiopia

Ethiopia had entered in to the process of decentralization before a formal federal arrangement was endorsed in 1995. The Ethiopian People's Revolutionary Democratic Front (EPRDF), the incumbent political party since 1991, encouraged the establishment of local government units along ethnic lines. This was deemed to be a necessary response to accommodate diversity

⁸ *ibid.*

⁹ Zemelak A Ayele, 'Decentralization, Development and Accommodation of Ethnic Minorities: The Case of Ethiopia' (Doctoral dissertation, University of Western Cape 2012) 55.

¹⁰ *ibid* 488.

¹¹ Van der Beken, *Completing the Constitutional Architecture*, above, 187.

which was considered to be the most pressing challenge of the country.¹² Proclamation number 7/1992 was instrumental for the beginning of the first phase of decentralization (1991-2001). The Proclamation also laid down the foundation for the Federal Constitution. It had listed 64 ethnic groups to establish their own ethnic self-administration.¹³ After ten years, the party realized that emphasizing only ethnicity leads to inefficiency in ensuring development and equitable service delivery and engaged in the further creation of new local governments and at some degree amalgamates certain of the existing ones.¹⁴ Indeed, in 2001, the District Level Decentralization Program(DLDP) launched by the federal government, administrative convenience, good governance and development issues began to be the salient justifications for strengthening the decentralization process.

Currently, there are no less than 60 political parties registered in Ethiopia. Based on their constituency, political parties often classified in to three: national, regional and local parties. They also could be categorized in to three based on their political programs: EPRDF, incumbent party and composed of four ethnic based parties representing regional states of, Amhara, Tigray, Oromiya and Southern Nations Nationalities and Peoples.¹⁵ EPRDF's affiliates are five in number which comprise Afar, Somali, Benishangul-Gumuz, Gmbella and Harari regional states.¹⁶ These parties are ethnic based and not opposition parties following EPRDF's ideological orientation. Except a few, most of the opposition parties are ethnic based; their constituencies are regional and local governments. Ethnic based local parties are mostly oppositions mainly seeking either regional statehood or new ethnic local government status. Member parties of EPRDF are represented by an equal number of people both in its executive committees and despite the obvious difference in population size each party is supposed to represent. Moreover, many agree that the TPLF was the most influential member of EPRDF.¹⁷ The party structure which controls all levels of government and its decision-making procedures on the principle of 'democratic centralism' affected local government creation and undermines the role of regional states in creating local government systems based on their circumstances.¹⁸ Following the 2016 protests in the country an increasing party fragmentation

¹²Zemelak A Ayele, 'The Politics of Sub-National Constitution and Local Government in Ethiopia' (2014) 6 Perspectives on Federalism 89, 109.

¹³ National/Regional Self Governments Establishment Proclamation no 7/1992, Art 3, Federal Negarit Gazeta, No 2.

¹⁴ Ayele, 'The Politics of Sub-National Constitution and Local Government in Ethiopia', above, 109.

¹⁵ Amhara National Democratic Movement (ANDM) currently called Amhara Democratic Party/ADP/. Tigray People Liberation Front (TPLF), the Oromo Peoples' Democratic Organization (OPDO) currently called Oromo Democratic Party/ODP/, and the Southern Ethiopian Peoples' Democratic Movement (SEPDM).

¹⁶ Afar National Democratic Party (ANDP), Somali People's Democratic Party (SPDP), Benishangul-Gumuz Peoples Democratic Party (BGPDP), Gambela people's Unity Democratic Movement (GPUDM), and Harari National League (HNL).

¹⁷ Following party fragmentations, this has been confirmed by the leaders of the remaining member parties as there was no equal power balance within and TPLF took the upper hand in decision-making and even interfering in the internal affairs of each member parties.

¹⁸ Ayele, 'The Politics of Sub-National Constitution and Local Government in Ethiopia', above, 90.

within EPRDF has been seen. This political dynamic changed the previous centralized nature of the party and TPLF has been relegated from its core position in the party.¹⁹ Enjoying this political liberalization opposition ethnic based local parties are getting more assertive in their claim of new territorial autonomy.

A City/Town administration, as the term implies, is established in urban areas. Based on classification, urban centers of Ethiopia are classified in five categories ranging from small towns to metropolitan City of Addis Ababa based on demographic size. According to Situational Analysis of IUSHS, the population size of small towns ranges from 2,000 to 20,000 people and constitute 80 per cent of total number of towns and only 33 per cent of urban population. The medium-sized towns range between 20,000 and 50,000, and hold 25 per cent of the urban population. Large-sized towns range between 50,000 and 100,000 people. There are 13 mega towns with a population between 100,000 and 500,000 people each. Addis Ababa is the only city in the country that hosts over 500,000 with about 3.5 million residents.²⁰

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¹⁹ Currently, the regional parties except TPLF and all affiliate parties have been merged in to one monolithic national party in the name of Prosperity Party.

²⁰ WSUP, 'Developing an Integrated Urban Sanitation and Hygiene Strategy and Strategic Action Plan for Ethiopia'.

WSUP Advisory, 'Developing an Integrated Urban Sanitation and Hygiene Strategy and Strategic Action Plan for Ethiopia'(Draft Situational Analysis for Ethiopia's IUSHS, 2015)

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